

Expropriation of property and its privatization

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Abstract: This article describes the expropriation of property from the state, its privatization, the application and importance of the applicable laws, the purpose and tasks of the adoption of the law, objects of privatization of state property, methods of privatization of state assets, etc.

Key words: State property, disposition, expropriation, privatization of property, object of privatization, methods of privatization

After Uzbekistan gained independence, the market form of the economy administrative economy during the former totalitarian regime by choice management through means, the state in civil dealings economic and legal development based on renunciation of hegemony determined the way. In this, especially, property reforms and relations to ownership that are not characteristic of a market economy radical change, correct distribution of material goods and ensuring property independence of subjects of economic transactions gained special importance. The first implemented in our country of the state in economic relations under property reforms change ownership position and layer of owners was forming. In this regard, the first one was carried out property reforms privatization of state-owned properties and aimed at decentralization, which is the first step in this area

State-owned residences and residence in these residences by privatizing the citizens on preferential terms was given.

Of course, conducting this process and its legal regulation. As a basis, civil legal instruments took an important place. Therefore, privatization is not only the implementation of this activity on privatization of the state body authorized to increase administrative-legal document, but also based on the payment of a fee or by issuing a state warrant on the condition of free property increased.

In this sense, on February 14, 2024, the Law «On Privatization of state property» was adopted. As stated in the preamble of the law, it defines the organizational and legal basis for changing the state property of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to create an effective, socially oriented market economy. In fact, expropriation and privatization of property is the most necessary condition of market relations.

Expropriation and privatization - property expropriation and privatization are manifested in various forms. Expropriation and privatization:

- transformation of the state enterprise into a public enterprise, economic society or company;
- turning the state enterprise into a rental enterprise with the possibility of purchasing the leased property in the future;
- sale of state property to non-state legal entities and individuals by selection and auction.

The previous Law «On Expropriation and Privatization» adopted in 1991 did not meet today's requirements, and this Law was amended and supplemented more than 20 times, making it obsolete.

The previous Law did not provide for privatization methods widely used abroad (in practice, 2 methods: auction, competition), requirements for openness and transparency, and specific powers of state bodies in the field of privatization.

For reference: In international experience, between 4 and 10 methods of privatization are used, including in Germany (6), the Czech Republic (7) and Poland (10).

Adoption of the law «On Privatization of State Property» serves as an important legal basis for deepening the process of privatization of state property, attracting investments to this state property, implementing new projects on the basis of inefficiently operating state property objects, and helping to harmonize legislation in the field of privatization of state property.

State property objects to be privatized include:

- state real estate objects;
- state shares (shares, shares);
- state unitary enterprises and state institutions.

State property can be fully or partially privatized, with the exception of non-privatizable state property provided for in the legislation on state property management.

Privatization of state property is carried out using the following methods:

- auction;
- competitive bidding;
- public invitation to negotiations;
- communication based on competition;

- stock trading;

- inclusion of a state unitary enterprise or a state institution as a state share in the authorized fund (authorized capital) of an economic company in the form of a property complex;

- inclusion of state shares and state real estate objects in the authorized fund (authorized capital) of the economic company as a state share;

- leasing the state unitary enterprise or state institution with the condition of subsequent privatization.

The choice of the method of privatization of state property is carried out by the competent state body or its regional departments, including on the basis of the recommendation of the engaged professional consultant.

The choice of the method of privatization of state property depends on the specific (individual, industry-related, regional and other) characteristics of the state real estate object, state unitary enterprise, state institution or economic society with a state share, financial and economic conditions. indicators and privatization goals are taken into account.

The competent state body or its regional departments have the right to make appropriate amendments and (or) additions to the "roadmap" for the privatization of state property in connection with changing the method of privatization of state property.

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